

SZ-HB-I-03 Search for a second degree studies (English)

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Doi	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10090660
ID	Sz-HB-I-03
Title	Search for a second degree studies
Educational area	#higher-education #adult-education
Persona	P: Carlotta - Without assignment https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14615153
Short description	Carlotta was a consultant in the Ministry of Food and Agriculture, is now retired and would like to study again. She informs herself about the course content and requirements for the course as well as enrollment and applies.
Result	Carlotta has applied for a degree through Hochschulstart
Process	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Problem scenario• Activity scenario<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Part 1: "Information about study models and requirements"• Part 2: "Identify digital skills"• Part 3: "Check suitability for a specific course of study"• Part 4: "Application"
Preconditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Carlotta is registered at BIRD• Carlotta is logged in to BIRD• Carlotta's BIRD account is linked to her data wallet
Components	#learningpathfinder #data-wallet #workspace
Services / tools	#Online-Self-Assessment #hochschulstart

Problem scenario

Introduction

Carlotta Pocelli, a retired woman and former advisor at the Ministry of Food and Agriculture in Berlin, has already studied and now wants to apply for a second degree. She would like to study nutritional science and would first like to find out more about the requirements and content of the course. She is particularly interested in how digital studying is these days and whether an online course might even be an option for her.

Problem definition

Carlotta wants to study and needs the right information. She wants to know whether she is ready for her chosen degree program. She wonders if she has the necessary skills, like younger students do, especially since the program is now much more digital than it was in the 1970s. Digitalization shapes everyday life, including higher education. Carlotta first wants to understand what this means for her and for her academic goals.

Background and context

Carlotta has already studied once, but that was quite a while ago. She therefore collects as much information as possible. She not only wants to know what's required for a second degree, but whether she has sufficient digital skills for a modern degree program. Using digital media (laptop, video conferencing tools, etc.) would be out of the question.

Impact of the problem (on the Persona)

Carlotta doesn't have as much time as the younger students and wouldn't apply until she's sure she can make it. But she doesn't want to postpone her dream any longer because she wants to do it now, not at age 75. So she needs the information, the tests, and the enrollment instructions now. She wants to make the right choice right away. Carlotta is a bit unsure.

Pre BIRD attempts at a solution

After browsing several university websites, Carlotta hasn't made much progress. She doesn't learn how up-to-date she needs to be with digital technology to be able to master her studies. Carlotta asks her children, which is not very enlightening. Reading long descriptions and instructions for tests and registering on unknown websites does not seem like a suitable approach to her. Carlotta has no desire for that. She would have preferred to take a simple self-assessment test to find out whether her skills are sufficient.

Activity scenario

Part 1: "Information about study models and requirements"

Step 1: Carlotta opens the LearningPathFinder and looks for information or (self-)tests that will help her better assess the skills she needs for her studies.

Carlotta therefore enters the following keywords into the LearningPathFinder: digital

skills in higher education

Step 2: Carlotta gets some resources with a list of frequently required skills or descriptions as a result. She wonders how she can find out if she meets these requirements.

Step 3: She opens the LearningPathFinder search again and enters the following keywords: “self-test”, “orientation” and “digital skills studies”.

Step 4: Carlotta is then offered several self-tests of varying length to help her determine her own level. Various universities in Germany and abroad offer tests, checklists, and even preparing courses that serve to achieve what Carlotta wants to achieve. The box lists just a selection of these:

- [Entry Requirements | Online Courses | The Open University](#)
- [Succeeding in postgraduate study](#)
- [Studie at the RemoteUni - does this suit me? - FernUniversität in Hagen](#)
- [Digital Readiness Index Germany | Cisco](#)
- Digital Readiness Test
- [A scale for self-assessment of digital skills among teacher training students Rubach Lazarides 2019.pdf](#)
- Online Self-Assessment (OSA) Uni Potsdam

Step 5: Carlotta goes to the Online Self-Assessment (OSA) website of the University of Potsdam [Home | OSA](#) and sees the specific test on nutritional science. She tells the LearningPathFinder to save it because she wants to take the test at a later time.

Step 6: Carlotta now selects the general digital competency test (OSA) and is redirected to the area where she can take it.

Step 7: She has the result sent to her data wallet. She now knows more about the degree of digitalization of her studies and can assess which skills she still needs to acquire.

Step 8: The LearningPathFinder suggests Carlotta to take an online self-assessment test on her preferred subject.

Part 2: "Identify digital skills"

Step 1: The next day, Carlotta accesses the learningPathFinder again and selects the Online Self-Assessment (OSA) website of the University of Potsdam [Home | OSA](#), where she is redirected. Since she already has an account there, she also completes the subject-specific OSA in Nutritional Sciences.

Step 2: Carlotta starts the “Nutritional Science” course.

Step 3: Carlotta is happy that she successfully completed the course. According to her OSA result, she would be suitable for the study. She would therefore like to apply for a place at university.

Step 4: She saves her personal result and the certificate in her data wallet.

Step 5: She liked the questions in the test and is now taking a closer look at how the nutritional science program in Potsdam is structured. She then decides that she'd like to apply there because it sounds like a good fit. So she goes to the page "Application to the University of Potsdam".

Part 3: "Check suitability for a specific course of study"

Step 1: Carlotta is shown the "Application to the University of Potsdam" page, including a task list for the next steps. She saves the page, whereupon BIRD asks her if she wants to save the to-do list from there as a to-do list in her personal area, and Carlotta agrees.

Step 2: Now she asks the LearningPathFinder again for more information about Hochschulstart. Here she learns that nutritional science is a restricted-entry subject and that, as a second-degree applicant, she is only allowed to submit one application for admission. Nevertheless, she registers with [Hochschulstart](#).

Step 3: Carlotta activates her account via email confirmation, logs in to the website, and is now registered.

Part 4: "Application"

Step 1: Carlotta updates her data wallet, opens it, connects to the Hochschulstart portal, and begins filling out the application form.

Step 2: Carlotta selects everything she needs for the application in her data wallet.

Step 3: At the same time, she continues to fill out the application form on Hochschulstart.

Step 4: Carlotta then agrees to the data transfer and can add her documents from her wallet to the application on Hochschulstart. Then she submits her application.